

Donar

Ecodesign for sustainable furniture

Donar focusses on environmental awareness, social impact and customer education through user experience by producing modular recycled and recyclable furniture

Highlights of innovative features

- The shell of the chair is made of felt produced of recycled plastic bottles.
- It is a modular furniture allowing for easy recycling and replacement of all parts.
- A product-service business model reduces the environmental impact and helps closing the material loop.

Donar has created NicoLess, a simple but unique chair made of recycled felt (60% recycled PP bottles and 40% non-woven textile) and designed by Primož Jeza Studio. No extra glue or binders are added. The shell and the metal base are linked with straps and can be combined in compositions of various lengths or stored in vertical stacks facilitating shipping and storage.

Company | Ownership of innovation

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DONAR d.o.o.
Gospodsvetska 10
1000 Ljubljana
Slovenia

donar.si

